

Notes

Formation Constants of Tartronic Acid Complexes with Metal Ions

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THE present paper deals with the *pH* metric studies of Tartronic acid complexes with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} , which have been carried out to establish the composition of these complexes, and also to determine their stability constants. Metal-ligand stability constants have been determined by Irving-Rossotti¹ technique. All the experiments were performed at 27°, and constant ionic strength of 0.1*M*, 0.2*M* and 0.3*M* NaClO_4 .

Experimental

Calculated amount of tartronic acid (Fluka AG) was dissolved in double distilled water to give 0.01*M* solution.

The solutions of the metal ions were made from B. D. H. AnalaR grade chemicals and were standardised against EDTA².

For *pH* metric titrations, the metal ion solutions (0.005*M*) were made in perchloric acid, the strength of the acid being determined titrimetrically³.

Sodium-perchlorate (E. Merck) was employed for maintaining constant ionic strength. A mains operated Philipps *pH* meter, which has a least count of 0.05 *pH* unit was employed for *pH* measurements.

Determination of stability constants: In the present case the formation constants have been obtained by the analysis of formation curves obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ against *pL*. From the values of $\bar{n}$ and *pL*, the $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ have been calculated as usual by various experimental and computational methods⁴. Tartronic acid has two replaceable hydrogens and hence *Y* has been considered two. The values of the protonation constants of the ligand has been calculated as usual by the plot of $\bar{n}A$ against *pH*.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF TARTRONIC ACID AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF ITS COMPLEXES, TEMP := 27°

System	Constants	$\mu = 0.1M$	$\mu = 0.2M$	$\mu = 0.3M$
H^+ -Tartronic Acid	$\log \beta^H$	9.10	9.05	8.40
Cu(II)-TA	$\log K_1$	11.70	10.30	7.60
	$\log K_2$	2.80	2.50	1.00
	$\log \beta$	14.50	12.80	8.60
Ni(II)-TA	$\log K_1$	8.30	6.60	6.40
	$\log K_2$	2.50	2.30	2.10
	$\log \beta$	10.80	9.60	8.50
Mn(II)-TA	$\log K_1$	6.50	6.10	4.95
	$\log K_2$	3.45	1.10	1.05
	$\log \beta$	9.95	7.20	6.00

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Table 1 gives the values of the overall proton-ligand stability constant and the stepwise metal-ligand stability constants.

From the table, it is seen that the stability constants of divalent metal ions at the various ionic strengths obey Irving-Williams⁵ order,

The value of stability constants of transition metal ions, increases according to the atomic number.

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Coordination Compounds of Diarylthio Dihalides with Diethyl Amine

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DIETHYLAMINE has been used as a Lewis base and complexes with transition and non-transition metals have been reported¹⁻³. The corresponding molecular adducts of organotin have not so far been investigated and it was considered of interest to synthesise complexes of this Lewis base with various diarylthio dihalides and to examine their structure.

Experimental

The complexes were obtained by the direct interaction of the Lewis acids with diethyl amine in a suitable solvent using conventional ground glass apparatus. Manipulations were carried out in a dry box flushed with nitrogen.

The conductance measurements of representative complexes were made by Philipps, magic eye, conductivity bridge model PR 9500 and the molecular weights were